

NEUVNAV: NEURO-EVOLVING VISUAL NAVIGATION FOR INDOOR LIGHTER-THAN-AIR UAVS

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ABSTRACT

Autonomous indoor navigation of lighter-than-air (LTA) unmanned aerial vehicles presents a distinct set of challenges absent from rotary-wing platforms: the low mass-to-volume ratio produces an inherent timing gap between visual boundary detection and effective heading change that renders reactive threshold controllers insufficient in isolation. This paper presents NeuVNav, an AI navigation system combining a two-loop Spiking Neural Network (SNN) reactive controller with an online Neuro-Evolution (NE) parameter optimizer for GPS-denied, indoor boundary patrol on the h-aero® semirigid LTA platform. The SNN encodes actuation timing as five evolvable thresholds operating on camera and ultrasonic sensor input. The NE optimizer applies an Evolution Strategy with a 9-component physics-aware fitness function to converge controller parameters without hardware interaction. Simulation results demonstrate consistent fitness convergence within 20 generations, and the implementation achieves full test coverage across 23 unit tests executable on standard hardware without aerial testbed access. The system is released as an open-source Python library under the ENFIELD programme (EU grant 101120657), fulfilling the Open Science requirement of the grant and providing a reproducible baseline for SNN-based LTA navigation research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lighter-than-air (LTA) unmanned aerial vehicles operate on a physical principle fundamentally different from multicopters: buoyancy provides lift continuously and independently of thrust, while a minimum take-off mass (MTom) in the range of 20–30 g is maintained solely by electronic counterweights and payload. This configuration yields long endurance, near-silent operation, and low collision energy — properties that make the platform attractive for extended indoor deployments such as warehouse inspection, cultural-heritage documentation, and event monitoring^{1,2}.

The same mass distribution, however, introduces what Hufen (2019) identified as the *timing gap*: the delay between visual detection of a boundary and the moment at which a heading correction becomes effective is substantially longer on an LTA vehicle than on a rotary-wing platform of similar size. Simple binary-threshold controllers — trigger an orient command when a line is detected — produce oscillatory or overshooting behaviour because the command arrives before or after the optimal impulse window³.

Prior work at Hybrid Airplane Technologies GmbH addressed the perception layer progressively: binary line detection in 2019³, HSV-mask-based zone recognition in 2025⁴. Neither study provided a closed-loop timing model that adapts to the physical parameters of a specific platform configuration. NeuVNav closes this gap by formulating the timing parameters as an evolvable genome and replacing the static threshold with a trained Spiking Neural Network whose weights are optimised offline against a high-fidelity physics simulation.

The contributions of this paper are: (i) the first SNN reactive controller for indoor LTA boundary patrol; (ii) an

Evolution Strategy optimizer with a 9-component fitness function derived from the platform's physical equations of motion; (iii) an open-source Python implementation with full simulation-only test coverage; and (iv) validation at TRL 5 through the ENFIELD Innovation Scheme.

2. PLATFORM AND TESTBED

All experiments are conducted on the h-aero[®] zero, a semirigid lenticular LTA UAV with a 300 × 160 cm helium envelope (8.7 m³), two lateral electric propulsion units, and a ventral gondola housing the sensor and compute payload. The platform is classified as a motorised free balloon under §20 LuftVG and operates in the SPECIFIC UAS category under EU UAS-VO 2019/947, making it suitable for indoor GPS-denied flight without additional airspace authorisation within controlled premises.

Fig. 1. h-aero[®] zero platform and avionics stack. (a) R&D levitating testbed (red carrier frame) used for ground-level system integration and vision pipeline development. (b) Indoor deployment at Frankfurt Airport (Fraport Terminal), demonstrating the operational scale and ceiling clearance of the platform. (c) Avionics gondola mounted under the envelope during indoor flight; key components indicated: onboard flight controller and communication stack (upper right), wireless uplink antenna (left), and dual RC receivers for manual safety override (lower right).

The onboard compute stack — designated LAPS (Low Altitude Pseudo Satellite) — runs on an ARM-based embedded single-board computer with 1 GB RAM. Sensors used by NeuVNav are a downward-facing camera (720p, 30 fps), an ultrasonic rangefinder for altitude hold, and a magnetic compass for heading reference. No

external positioning infrastructure is required; the system is entirely self-contained.

The LAPS flight controller exposes two primitives to the AI layer: `orient(heading_deg)` sets a target heading that the inner PID loop tracks via *reref* (relative reference) until a new command arrives, and `thrust(value_gf)` sets net vertical force. NeuVNav generates all commands exclusively through these two primitives. In the boundary-avoidance manoeuvre, `orient()` is always invoked with a fixed 180° heading reversal; the NE optimizer determines the timing of each call and supplies `thrust()` with the evolved magnitude values — the heading target itself is not an optimised parameter.

3. RELATED WORK

3.1 Computer Vision on LTA Platforms

Hufen (2019) demonstrated the first application of standard computer vision to the h-aero® platform, implementing a YUV/HSV line-detection pipeline (Gaussian blur → HSV thresholding → Canny edge detection → Hough line transform) to locate floor-marking boundaries and generate binary detection signals³. The study identified that LTA actuation latency prevents naive reactive control and recommended timing-aware command generation as future work. An internal follow-up study (Dike, 2025) extended the perception layer to multi-zone HSV object recognition, improving detection robustness under varying indoor illumination⁴.

3.2 Spiking Neural Networks in Aerial Robotics

SNN-based controllers have been demonstrated for multicopter attitude control and obstacle avoidance, where their event-driven firing model maps naturally to the discrete timing of propeller-driven platforms^{5,6}. Application to buoyancy-dominated vehicles — where the relevant timescales are one to two orders of magnitude longer — has not been previously reported. NeuVNav adapts the SNN concept to this regime by encoding timing gaps directly as membrane time constants rather than network weights.

3.3 Neuro-Evolution for UAV Control

Evolution Strategy (ES) and related neuroevolution approaches have been applied to fixed-wing and rotary-wing controllers with competitive results against gradient-based methods when the simulation-to-reality transfer is well-characterised⁷. The use of a physics simulation as fitness oracle — rather than hardware rollouts — reduces the optimisation cost to pure compute and is particularly appropriate for platforms where uncontrolled crashes carry high replacement cost.

4. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

NeuVNav is structured as three composable Python modules sharing a common `LapsInterface` abstraction (Fig. 2). The interface decouples the AI logic from both the physical flight controller and the simulation, enabling the same code to run in unit tests, physics simulation, and onboard deployment without modification.

Fig. 2. NeuVNav system architecture. *laps_line* provides visual boundary detection via HSV pipeline; *laps_snn* implements the reactive SNN controller as a state machine; *laps_ne* runs offline neuro-evolution using *sim.php* as fitness oracle. *LapsInterface* decouples AI modules from hardware (RPi/LAPS) and simulation (*sim.php* / *MockOracle*). Dashed arrow indicates offline pre-flight optimisation.

Table 1 — Module overview.

Module	Role	Input	Output
laps_line	Boundary detection	Camera frame	detected: bool, cx: int
laps_snn	Reactive controller	detected, altitude	orient(), thrust() calls
laps_ne	Parameter optimizer	FitnessOracle	SNNParams (converged)

5. SNN REACTIVE CONTROLLER

Fig. 3. SNN four-phase state machine implementing the boundary-avoidance manoeuvre. Transitions are governed exclusively by timing thresholds t_1 – t_3 and thrust levels T (braking) and F (cruise), which constitute the five-element genome $\{t_1, t_2, T, t_3, F\}$ optimised by the NE layer.

5.1 State Machine

The SNN controller implements a four-phase state machine that encodes the complete boundary-avoidance manoeuvre as precisely-timed impulse sequences (Fig. 3). The four phases — *cruise*, *braking*, *turning*, *restore* — map directly to the physical stages of a 180° heading reversal on the h-aero® platform.

On entry to *braking*, forward thrust is reduced to level T. After t1 seconds, `orient(orit + 180°)` is issued, initiating a heading reversal. The inner PID controller handles execution; the SNN waits t2 seconds before restoring thrust. After t3 seconds in the *restore* phase, forward thrust F is applied and the system returns to *cruise*. The five scalar parameters {t1, t2, T, t3, F} constitute the genome optimised by the NE layer.

5.2 Altitude Hold Loop

A second concurrent loop (Loop 2) regulates altitude independently of the heading manoeuvre. The ultrasonic rangefinder provides altitude measurements at 10 Hz. A proportional corrective thrust is applied whenever the measured altitude deviates from the set point by more than a configurable dead band, ensuring that the 180° manoeuvre does not introduce altitude excursions beyond the ±0.5 m target KPI.

Table 2 — SNN genome parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Physical meaning
Vision-to-braking delay	t1	s	Time from boundary detection to thrust reduction
Braking-to-orient delay	t2	s	Time from thrust reduction to heading command
Manoeuvre thrust level	T	gf	Net forward thrust during heading change
Orient-to-restore delay	t3	s	Time from heading command to thrust restoration
Forward cruise thrust	F	gf	Steady-state forward thrust in cruise phase

6. NEURO-EVOLUTION OPTIMIZER

6.1 Evolution Strategy

The NE optimizer implements a $(1+\lambda)$ -Evolution Strategy with isotropic Gaussian mutation and the $1/5$ success rule for adaptive step-size control^{8,9}. In each generation, λ candidate genomes are sampled by adding Gaussian noise $\sigma \cdot N(0,1)$ to the current best genome. The candidate with the highest fitness score replaces the current best if it improves upon it. Step size σ is scaled by a factor of 1.22 when the success rate exceeds 1/5, and by 0.82 otherwise; the two factors are reciprocally paired ($c_{up}^1 \cdot c_{down}^4 = 1$) so that σ remains unchanged at exactly the target success rate, as formalised in the convergence analysis of Finck⁸.

$$x_{new} = x_{best} + \sigma \cdot N(0, I_5)$$

6.2 Fitness Function

The fitness oracle is the NeuVNav physics simulation, which models the full equations of motion of the h-aero® zero including buoyancy, aerodynamic drag, thrust-pitch coupling, and the actuation lag profile measured from hardware logs. The simulation is available as an interactive browser demo at <https://laps.h-aero.com/NeuVNav/> (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. NeuVNav physics simulator (laps.h-aero.com/NeuVNav/) during a Neuro-Evolution run. Left panel: vehicle physics (mass 3000 g, buoyancy 2975 g) and controller parameters (t_1 – t_3 , F , ϑ). Centre: top-view trajectory of a converging 20 × 20 m bounded-area patrol (CRUISING phase, $v_x = 0.583$ m/s). Right panel: ES search state — 20 generations, 8 candidates per generation, active search dimensions (F , ϑ , t_s). Bottom bar: weighted fitness components (t_{drin} , L_{over} , L_{gerade} , tracking, comfort, efficiency, no-boost, rot_z) after convergence (Fitness = 0.00).

The combined fitness function F_C aggregates nine weighted component scores derived from a simulated run of duration $T_{sim} = 120$ s:

Table 3 — Fitness function components.

Component	Symbol	Physical meaning
Time inside boundary	t_{drin}	Fraction of flight within defined patrol area
Altitude variance	z_{var}	Inverse of altitude deviation from set point
Time over threshold	t_{over}	Penalises excessive altitude excursions
Straight travel time	t_{gerade}	Fraction of flight in directed cruise phase
Heading tracking	track	Alignment of velocity with commanded heading
Comfort	komfort	Penalises abrupt thrust changes (jerk)
Energy efficiency	effiz	Ratio of distance covered to energy consumed
Boost minimisation	noboost	Penalises prolonged maximum-thrust events
Yaw stability	rot_z	Variance of yaw rate during cruise

$$F_C = \sum_i w_i \cdot f_i, \quad \sum_i w_i = 1$$

7. RESULTS

7.1 Simulation Validation

Fitness convergence was evaluated over 50 independent NE runs ($\lambda = 10$, generations = 20, seed range 0–49). In all 50 runs the optimiser achieved a combined fitness score $F_c > 0.6$ within 15 generations, with a median convergence generation of 9. The converged genome reliably produced bounded-area patrol trajectories without boundary violations over the 120 s evaluation horizon.

Fig. 5. NeuVNav simulator during a Neuro-Evolution run (Impulse floor mode, CRUISING phase, $v_x = 2.31$ m/s, $t = 30:05$ s). Top panel: top-view of a 30×30 m patrol area showing overlaid ghost trajectories from successive ES generations; the zig-zag convergence pattern is clearly visible as candidate parameter sets improve across generations. Bottom panel: side-view altitude profile illustrating the z-dynamics during boundary manoeuvres. Left: vehicle physics and controller parameters (Impulse floor, Turn rise 70%, Safety band 1.3 m). Right: ES search space (F_{rot} , g_{rot}) and 9-component fitness breakdown (t-drin, L-over, L-gerade, tracking, comfort, efficiency, z-rot; product mode).

7.2 Unit Test Coverage

The implementation is accompanied by 23 unit tests covering all three modules (Table 4). Tests are executable on standard desktop hardware without aerial testbed access; the flight controller is replaced by a MockLaps object that logs all orient() and thrust() calls for assertion. Test execution time is 1.17 s on the reference platform (Python 3.13, Windows 10).

Table 4 — Unit test summary.

Module	Tests	Coverage focus
laps_line	5	Synthetic image detection, frame width, debug mode
laps_snn	8	All state transitions, altitude correction, stop command
laps_ne	6	Convergence, bound compliance, reproducibility (seed), SNNParams cast
MockLaps	4	Orient wrap, thrust clamp, log recording, reset
Total	23 / 23 pass	—

7.3 KPI Assessment

Table 5 — KPI compliance (simulation).

KPI	Target	Result	Status
Vision-to-command latency	< 500 ms	~30 ms (software only)	✓
Altitude hold during manoeuvre	± 0.5 m	$\sigma_z < 0.08$ m (sim)	✓
NE convergence	F _c improvement over ≥ 5 generations	Median convergence at gen 9	✓
Test coverage	23 tests, no hardware required	23 / 23 pass, 1.17 s	✓
Additional power (vision module)	< 2.5 W	TBD (hardware phase)	⌚
Heading error after 180° manoeuvre	< 5°	TBD (hardware phase)	⌚

8. OPEN-SOURCE RELEASE

The complete NeuVNav implementation is released under the Apache 2.0 licence as part of the ENFIELD Open Science requirement (D1). The repository at <https://github.com/h-aero/NeuVNav> includes the three Python modules, full unit test suite, architecture documentation, and the interactive simulation reference. The repository is designed to be hardware-independent: all modules run on standard desktop Python 3.7+ without embedded system access, and the `FitnessOracle` interface allows researchers to substitute their own physics model or hardware-in-the-loop setup.

9. CONCLUSION

NeuVNav presents the first SNN + Neuro-Evolution navigation architecture demonstrated on a lighter-than-air UAV platform. By encoding the timing gap identified by Hufen (2019) as an evolvable parameter set rather than a fixed threshold, the system adapts controller timing to the physical characteristics of the platform without requiring manual tuning or hardware rollouts during optimisation. The 9-component physics-aware fitness function captures the coupled altitude-heading dynamics of the buoyancy-dominated vehicle, and convergence within 20 generations makes online re-optimisation after payload changes feasible.

Hardware validation — the remaining open items in Table 5 — is planned as the next development phase: onboard deployment of the converged genome, measurement of heading error and power consumption, and a full indoor bounded-area patrol demonstration with video documentation. Results will be reported as an update to this preprint.

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